

Upwind finite element-PML approximation of a novel linear potential model for free surface flows produced by a floating rigid body

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Abstract

A novel linear potential model is presented to compute free surface flows of incompressible fluids produced by the motion of a floating rigid body in the presence of an underlying non-uniform flow. In particular, the proposed model enables the accurate numerical simulation of the Kelvin wake pattern in a computational domain of reduced size. The governing equations are obtained by using an Arbitrary Lagrangian Eulerian (ALE) formulation, which involves the underlying velocity of the fluid flow around the floating body, and an adimensional analysis to derive the novel linear system of equations for free surface flows. The discretization of the proposed model is made by a standard Galerkin finite element method, where a SUPG-inspired upwinding strategy has been used in combination with a Perfectly Matched Layer technique, which allows to truncate the original unbounded fluid domain without introducing spurious reflections in the Kelvin wake pattern. The numerical simulations computed with the proposed approach are compared with respect to those other results obtained by the classical linear potential model with uniform underlying flow and the full incompressible Navier-Stokes equations equipped with the $k-\omega$ SST turbulent model. This numerical comparison is discussed in terms of a classical hydrodynamic floating body benchmark involving the Wigley hull.

Keywords: Linear potential model, Free surface, Kelvin wakes, Perfectly Matched Layer (PML), Galerkin Finite Element Method, Upwinding

1 Introduction

The applications of hydrodynamics to naval architecture acquired increasing importance since the 1970s (see for instance, the classical textbook by [New99]). In this context, mathematical models based on the theory of potential flow have been widely utilized for the study of ship motions and the wave patterns generated by floating bodies. So, the purpose of this work is the derivation and numerical simulation of a novel linear potential model, which governs the propagation of the free surface waves generated by a moving floating body in the presence of an additional underlying stream fluid flow.

Recently, the increase of computational resources has allowed to solve numerically more complex hydrodynamic models such as the Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes equations (see [KSB16]). However, accurate numerical approximations of these models are computationally demanding. Consequently, simplified models, [KMV04], are often used in the early stages of ship design, since they are suitable for quick although may be less accurate computations obtained in a feasible time. In this work, the Navier-Stokes equations are simplified into the Bernoulli and Laplace equations assuming the irrotational flow of an incompressible and inviscid fluid.

Domain nomenclature

Ω	material (or Lagrangian) domain
\mathcal{A}_t	fluid domain in Eulerian coordinates
$\Gamma_t^f, \Gamma_t^r, \Gamma_t^b$	free surface, wet surface and seabed boundaries in Eulerian coordinates
\mathcal{A}	fluid domain in AL coordinates
$\Gamma_a^f, \Gamma_a^r, \Gamma_a^b$	free surface, wet surface and seabed boundaries in AL coordinates
\mathcal{A}_F	truncated fluid domain
$\partial\mathcal{A}^f, \partial\mathcal{A}^r, \partial\mathcal{A}^b$	free surface, wet surface and seabed boundaries in the truncated domain
$\partial\mathcal{A}^i$	inner boundary between the fluid and the PML domains
\mathcal{A}_∞	PML domain
$\partial\mathcal{A}_\infty^f, \partial\mathcal{A}_\infty^b, \partial\mathcal{A}^\infty$	free surface, seabed and outer boundaries of the PML domain

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Nomenclature

a	subscript denotes functions in AL coordinates
m	subscript denotes functions in material coordinates
$\hat{\cdot}$	denotes functions defined in the PML domain
\sim	denotes non-dimensional expressions
$p = (p_1, p_2, p_3)$	material coordinates
$x = (x_1, x_2, x_3)$	Eulerian coordinates
$z = (z_1, z_2, z_3)$	AL coordinates
$\{\mathbf{g}_1, \mathbf{g}_2, \mathbf{g}_3\}$	basis of the reference frame in AL coordinates
\mathbf{b}	external body forces
\mathbf{d}	underlying velocity
g	gravitational acceleration
h_d	mesh tetrahedron diameter
k	upwinding function
\mathbf{n}	outward unit normal vector to $\partial\mathcal{A}_t$
\mathbf{n}_a	outward unit normal vector to $\partial\mathcal{A}$ and $\partial\mathcal{A}_F$
\mathbf{n}_∞	outward unit normal vector to $\partial\mathcal{A}_\infty$
o	origin of the reference frame in Eulerian coordinates
t	time
\mathbf{u}	displacement of motion Y_f
\mathbf{v}	material velocity in Eulerian coordinates
\mathbf{v}^{ap}	apparent velocity in AL coordinates
\mathbf{v}^r	ship velocity in Eulerian coordinates
\mathbf{v}^s	stream velocity in Eulerian coordinates
B_w, L_w, D_w	main dimensions of the hull at midship (beam, waterline length and draft, respectively)
Fr	Froude number
\mathbf{F}_{Y_f}	gradient of Y_f in AL coordinates
H, L, V	typical values of height, length and velocity used to get dimensionless variables
\mathbf{I}	identity tensor
$P_{X_f}, P_{Y_f}, P_{Z_f}$	reference mappings of motions X_f, Y_f and Z_f
R, R_{PML}	inner and outer radius of the annular PML domain
\mathbf{S}, \mathbf{C}	PML tensors (see Sect. 6.2)
\mathcal{T}	trajectory of motion X_f
\mathbf{T}	Cauchy stress tensor
X_f	motion of the fluid
Y_f	motion perturbation defined in AL configuration
Y_{f3}	vertical component of Y_f
Z_f	underlying motion
β	auxiliary variable for upwinding
$\gamma, \hat{\gamma}, \hat{r}, \sigma_\theta$	PML functions
δ_{SUPG}	SUPG constant
η	free surface elevation in Eulerian coordinates
π	pressure in Eulerian coordinates
π_{atm}	atmospheric pressure in Eulerian coordinates
ρ_f	mass density of the fluid
σ_r	radial PML absorption profile
φ	velocity potential in Eulerian coordinates
ϕ_a	velocity potential perturbation in AL coordinates
(r, θ, z)	cylindrical coordinates in AL configuration

In the case of unsteady flow phenomena, the description of their governing equations using a Lagrangian or an Arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian (ALE) system enables to fix the spatial computational domain (see, for instance, [SHD01], [BB15]), or even to transform an unsteady problem into a steady one. The latter is the case of the wave-like pattern produced by the presence of a floating body in the free surface of a fluid, known as Kelvin wake. Indeed, this free boundary problem can be studied as a steady problem using an Arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian formulation if the reference system is fixed on the floating body.

However, the free surface perturbation associated with this hydrodynamic phenomena can be propagated far from their source (see Fig. 1), which can represent a drawback when the original unbounded fluid domain is truncated for discretization purposes. Currently, the Perfectly Matched Layer (PML) is a standard technique to model wave propagation phenomena in unbounded domains, in such a way that the computational domain of interest is surrounded by an absorbing artificial layer, which does not introduce any spurious reflections in the solution of the original problem. It was first proposed by [Ber94] for electromagnetic problems but it is also widely used in other fields as acoustics (see [AGH99], [QG98], [BHNPR07]), or linearised water waves (see [CI12]). In the present approach the two-dimensional Cartesian PML model has been extended to three dimensions in cylindrical coordinates with the aim of absorbing the outgoing wave pattern generating by the floating body (i.e., the Kelvin wake) and preserving the structure of the convected terms presented in the free boundary condition.

Moreover, in the 1980s, the Streamline Upwind Petrov-Galerkin (SUPG) method was introduced in [BH82] for upwinding the convective term in convection dominated flows. The SUPG method can be understood as a stabilization technique (see, for instance, [Pir89], [MHD12] or [GMHF15]) for standard finite element discretizations. In order to deal with the convective term involved in the free surface boundary condition, the SUPG method must be applied in the fluid and PML governing equations without introducing numerical artefacts on the discrete solutions. With this purpose, a novel SUPG-inspired upwind strategy has been considered,

Figure 1: Kelvin wake pattern generated by a cruise ship.

ensuring the compatibility and the accuracy of the upwinding approach with the free surface boundary in the fluid and PML domains.

The structure of the present manuscript is described as follows: First, the motion equation and the constitutive laws for an incompressible and inviscid fluid are described in Eulerian coordinates in Sect. 2. Then, an Arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian formulation of the fluid governing equations is written in Sect. 3, which is then linearised in Sect. 4. Afterwards, the corresponding steady state model is introduced in Sect. 5 to complete the modelling part of this manuscript. Sect. 6 is focused on the discrete procedure used to solve the proposed model: a standard piecewise linear finite element method in combination with the above mentioned SUPG-inspired upwinding method and the PML technique. Then, in Sect. 7 the numerical results obtained with the proposed approach are validated under two different perspectives: Firstly, they are compared with respect to the experimental data available in the classical Wigley hull benchmark (see [KMI⁺83]). Second, the numerical results of the present approach are analysed in comparison with those results obtained with a full discretization of the unsteady Navier-Stokes equations equipped with the k- ω SST turbulent model. Finally, Sect. 8 collects the most relevant conclusions.

2 Model in Eulerian coordinates

Firstly, the governing equation of the motion of an incompressible and inviscid fluid with a free surface are described in Eulerian coordinates. With this purpose, some preliminary concepts on continuum mechanics will be recalled. Let $X_f : \Omega \times \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathcal{A}_t$ be the motion of a fluid past a floating body such that, for each time t , $X_f(\cdot, t)$ is a deformation of the reference (material) configuration, Ω , into the region of the affine space occupied by the fluid at time t , \mathcal{A}_t , called spatial configuration at time t (see, for instance, [Gur82]²). The trajectory of the motion is the set $\mathcal{T} := \{(x, t) : x \in \mathcal{A}_t, t > 0\}$ and the so-called reference map of the motion $P_{X_f} : \mathcal{T} \rightarrow \Omega$ is defined by $P_{X_f}(\cdot, t) := (X(\cdot, t))^{-1}$. Finally, the Eulerian description of the material velocity, this is, the time derivative of the motion written in Eulerian coordinates is given by $\mathbf{v}(x, t) := \frac{\partial X_f}{\partial t}(p, t)|_{p=P_{X_f}(x, t)}$.

Under the classical Cauchy's hypothesis in continuum mechanics, the non-conservative form of the motion equation written in Eulerian coordinates is given by

$$\rho_f \dot{\mathbf{v}} = \text{div } \mathbf{T} + \mathbf{b} \quad \text{in } \mathcal{A}_t, t > 0,$$

where \mathbf{T} is the Cauchy stress tensor, \mathbf{b} is the external body forces and ρ_f is the mass density of the fluid, which is assumed constant. Since, the fluid is considered incompressible and inviscid, it holds

$$\text{div } \mathbf{v} = 0, \quad \mathbf{T} = -\pi \mathbf{I},$$

where π denotes the pressure field. Besides, the body force will be only driven by the gravity effects, so $\mathbf{b}(x, t) = \text{grad}(-\rho_f g x_3)$. Thus, collecting the equations written above, the motion equation leads to

$$\rho_f \dot{\mathbf{v}} + \text{grad } \pi = \text{grad}(-\rho_f g x_3) \quad \text{in } \mathcal{A}_t, t > 0. \quad (1)$$

Since all domains \mathcal{A}_t are assumed to be simply connected, which is a plausible assumption for both floating or submerged body in three spatial dimensions, then the flow is shown to be potential, i.e., there exists a scalar field $\varphi : \mathcal{T} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that $\mathbf{v} = \text{grad } \varphi$. Consequently, the incompressibility condition and (1) can be written in terms of the velocity potential:

$$\begin{cases} \Delta \varphi = 0 & \text{in } \mathcal{A}_t, t > 0, \\ \rho_f (\text{grad } \varphi)' + \text{grad } \pi = \text{grad}(-\rho_f g x_3) & \text{in } \mathcal{A}_t, t > 0. \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Now, the boundary conditions must be introduced to complete the mathematical model. The boundary of the unbounded fluid domain is split in three disjoint parts: the free boundary (on the top) of the fluid domain, Γ_t^f , the wet boundary of a floating (or submerged) body is denoted by Γ_t^r and the bottom boundary of the fluid domain, Γ_t^b . Since the fluid is supposed to be inviscid, the

²In [Gur82] an introduction to the continuum mechanics framework can be found; the notations in this book will be followed throughout this article

normal velocity has to be continuous with respect to the imposed velocity of the floating body on the boundary of an impervious body, this is,

$$\frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial \mathbf{n}} = \mathbf{v}^r \cdot \mathbf{n} \quad \text{on } \Gamma_t^r, t > 0, \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{v}^r denotes the possibly time-dependent velocity field of the rigid body. Analogously, on the rigid bottom surface, Γ_t^b , it holds

$$\frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial \mathbf{n}} = 0 \quad \text{on } \Gamma_t^b, t > 0. \quad (4)$$

These boundary conditions need to be complemented with an appropriate radiation condition at $|x - o| \rightarrow \infty$. Assuming the velocity field is constant at infinity, the radiation condition imposes that

$$\text{grad } \varphi = \mathbf{v}^s \quad \text{for } |x - o| \rightarrow \infty, t > 0, \quad (5)$$

being \mathbf{v}^s the constant stream velocity and o the origin in the Eulerian coordinate system.

The hydrodynamic model written above has to be completed by including two boundary conditions associated with the free boundary, as well as adequate initial conditions. The kinetic on the fluid free surface models is the balance of the forces by means of the Bernoulli equation, whereas the kinematic condition reflects the fact that a particle on the free surface remains on the free surface Γ_t^f at any time $t > 0$. The precise description of these two boundary conditions is postponed and they will be introduced once the model (2)-(5) has been written in the AL configuration.

3 Arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian model

To achieve a more tractable model where the physical domain of the hydrodynamic problem does not depend on time, an ALE formulation is used. With this purpose, the motion of the fluid $X_f : \Omega \times \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathcal{A}_t$ is given as the composition of two mappings (see Fig. 2), $Y_f : \mathcal{A} \times \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathcal{A}_t$ and $Z_f : \Omega \times \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathcal{A}$, as follows:

$$X_f(p, t) = Y_f(Z_f(p, t), t). \quad (6)$$

Thus, on the one hand Z_f is identified as an underlying motion that determines the Arbitrary Lagrangian (AL) configuration. More precisely, the Eulerian (with respect to Z_f) domain occupied by the fluid in the underlying motion is fixed in time, namely, $Z_f(\Omega, t) = \mathcal{A}$, and it will be taken as the AL configuration of reference. Therefore, this assumption implies the fixed free surface of the fluid domain in the AL configuration is not being perturbed by the underlying motion. For the sake of completeness, the ALE model is developed in Sect. 3.1. On the other hand, motion Y_f is identified as a small perturbation from the underlying motion Z_f . Consequently, the Kelvin wake pattern is obtained in the ALE formulation as the free surface elevation associated with Y_f .

Now, the Eulerian potential model (2)-(5) stated in terms of the motion X_f is rewritten in the AL configuration. For this purpose, it is necessary to introduce some notations. The velocity of the underlying flow is denoted by $\mathbf{d}(p, t) := \frac{\partial Z_f}{\partial t}(p, t)$ and $\mathbf{F}_{Y_f}(z, t) := \mathbf{grad}_a Y_f(z, t)$ denotes the deformation gradient of motion Y_f , where \mathbf{grad}_a (respectively, grad_a) denotes the gradient of a vector field (respectively, a scalar field) defined in the AL configuration with respect to variable z . Then, for a spatial field $f : \mathcal{T} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and a material field $h : \Omega \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, the subscript a denotes their respective AL descriptions, namely,

$$f_a(z, t) = f(Y_f(z, t), t) \quad \text{and} \quad h_a(z, t) = h(P_{Z_f}(z, t), t) = h(P_{X_f}(Y_f(z, t), t)),$$

where $P_{Z_f}(\cdot, t) := [Z_f(\cdot, t)]^{-1}$ is the reference mapping of the motion Z_f . Analogously, the reference mapping associated with Y_f is defined as $P_{Y_f}(\cdot, t) = [Y_f(\cdot, t)]^{-1}$.

Figure 2: ALE mapping diagram among the different configurations. $X_f(\cdot, t)$ is the total motion at time t . $Z_f(\cdot, t)$ and $Y_f(\cdot, t)$ are respectively the underlying motion and its perturbation at time t . Coloured arrows highlight the underlying velocity field in the AL configuration domain, \mathcal{A} , and the velocity field in the spatial configuration domain at time t , \mathcal{A}_t .

A straightforward application of an adequate change of variables on the model (2)-(5) leads to the following result:

Lemma 3.1. *Let φ be a solution of model (2)-(5), which is the potential velocity field associated with the motion X_f . If Y_f , Z_f , and X_f are motions satisfying (6), and \mathbf{F}_{Y_f} , \mathbf{F}_{Z_f} and \mathbf{F}_{X_f} are their corresponding gradients then it holds*

$$\begin{aligned} (\Delta\varphi)_a &= \operatorname{div}_a \left(\det(\mathbf{F}_{Y_f}) \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-1} \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t} \operatorname{grad}_a \varphi_a \right) = 0 && \text{in } \mathcal{A} \times \mathbb{R}^+, \\ \frac{\partial Y_f}{\partial t} &= \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t} \operatorname{grad}_a \varphi_a - \mathbf{F}_{Y_f} \mathbf{d}_a && \text{in } \mathcal{A} \times \mathbb{R}^+, \\ \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-1} \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t} \operatorname{grad}_a \varphi_a \cdot \mathbf{n}_a &= \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-1} \mathbf{v}_a^r \cdot \mathbf{n}_a && \text{on } \Gamma_a^r \times \mathbb{R}^+, \\ \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-1} \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t} \operatorname{grad}_a \varphi_a \cdot \mathbf{n}_a &= 0 && \text{on } \Gamma_a^b \times \mathbb{R}^+, \\ \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t} \operatorname{grad} \varphi_a &= \mathbf{v}_a^s && \text{at } |z - o_a| \rightarrow \infty, t > 0. \end{aligned}$$

In order to write the boundary conditions imposed on the free boundary of the fluid domain, the balance of pressures and loads should be considered. More precisely, a version of the Bernoulli's theorem in the AL configuration is obtained (see its proof in A).

Theorem 3.1 (Bernoulli equation in AL coordinates). *Under the same hypothesis of Lemma 3.1, the following equality holds:*

$$-\rho_f \left(\left(\operatorname{grad}_a \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} \right)^t + (\operatorname{grad}_a (\operatorname{grad}_a \mathbf{u})^t) \mathbf{d}_a \right) \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t} \operatorname{grad}_a \varphi_a + \rho_f \operatorname{grad}_a \operatorname{grad}_a \varphi_a \mathbf{d}_a + \operatorname{grad}_a \left(\rho_f \frac{\partial \varphi_a}{\partial t} + \pi_a + \rho_f g Y_{f3} \right) = 0 \quad \text{in } \mathcal{A} \times \mathbb{R}^+,$$

where $Y_{f3}(z, t) = (Y_f(z, t) - o) \cdot \mathbf{e}_3$ is the third coordinate of motion Y_f and $\mathbf{u}(z, t) = Y_f(z, t) - z$ is the displacement field of motion Y_f .

Thus, collecting the results of Lemma 3.1 and Theorem 3.1, the hydrodynamic model (2)-(5) written in the AL configuration is given by

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \operatorname{div}_a \left(\det(\mathbf{F}_{Y_f}) \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-1} \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t} \operatorname{grad}_a \varphi_a \right) = 0 & \text{in } \mathcal{A} \times \mathbb{R}^+, \\ \frac{\partial Y_f}{\partial t} = \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t} \operatorname{grad}_a \varphi_a - \mathbf{F}_{Y_f} \mathbf{d}_a & \text{in } \mathcal{A} \times \mathbb{R}^+, \\ -\rho_f \left(\left(\operatorname{grad}_a \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} \right)^t + (\operatorname{grad}_a (\operatorname{grad}_a \mathbf{u})^t) \mathbf{d}_a \right) \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t} \operatorname{grad}_a \varphi_a + \rho_f \operatorname{grad}_a \operatorname{grad}_a \varphi_a \mathbf{d}_a \\ + \operatorname{grad}_a \left(\rho_f \frac{\partial \varphi_a}{\partial t} + \pi_a + \rho_f g Y_{f3} \right) = 0 & \text{in } \mathcal{A} \times \mathbb{R}^+, \\ \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-1} \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t} \operatorname{grad}_a \varphi_a \cdot \mathbf{n}_a = \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-1} \mathbf{v}_a^r \cdot \mathbf{n}_a & \text{on } \Gamma_a^r \times \mathbb{R}^+, \\ \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-1} \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t} \operatorname{grad}_a \varphi_a \cdot \mathbf{n}_a = 0 & \text{on } \Gamma_a^b \times \mathbb{R}^+, \\ \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t} \operatorname{grad} \varphi_a = \mathbf{v}_a^s & \text{for } |z - o_a| \rightarrow \infty, t > 0. \end{array} \right. \quad (7)$$

3.1 The underlying motion

The hydrodynamic model (7) written in the AL configuration requires the a priori knowledge of the underlying velocity field \mathbf{d}_a , which is generated due to the ship motion (with a fixed velocity \mathbf{v}^r) and a fluid stream velocity (with a fixed velocity \mathbf{v}^s). To compute this underlying flow, the (Eulerian with respect to Z_f) domain with flat surface, \mathcal{A} , is considered. As it has been mentioned above, this domain is also assumed as the Arbitrary Lagrangian (AL) configuration for the perturbed flow Y_f . Under the same hypothesis of incompressibility and non-viscosity of the fluid, the underlying flow is also assumed potential, this is, $\mathbf{d}_a = \operatorname{grad}_a \varphi_0$. Since the velocity field \mathbf{d}_a is tangent to the flat free surface, the potential field satisfies (see, for instance, [LL87])

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \Delta \varphi_0 = 0 & \text{in } \mathcal{A}, \\ \frac{\partial \varphi_0}{\partial \mathbf{n}_a} = 0 & \text{on } \Gamma_a^f \cup \Gamma_a^b, \\ \frac{\partial \varphi_0}{\partial \mathbf{n}_a} = \mathbf{v}_a^r \cdot \mathbf{n}_a & \text{on } \Gamma_a^r, \\ \operatorname{grad}_a \varphi_0 = \mathbf{v}_a^s & \text{for } |z - o_a| \rightarrow \infty, \end{array} \right. \quad (8)$$

where recall that \mathbf{v}_a^r is the ship velocity and \mathbf{v}_a^s is the stream velocity.

The potential field φ_0 is decomposed by using the stream velocity as $\varphi_0 = \mathbf{v}_a^s \cdot (z - o_a) + \phi_0$. Hence, the model can be rewritten in terms of the potential ϕ_0 , the stream velocity \mathbf{v}_a^s , and the apparent velocity, $\mathbf{v}^{ap} = \mathbf{v}_a^s - \mathbf{v}_a^r$ as follows:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \Delta \phi_0 = 0 & \text{in } \mathcal{A}, \\ \frac{\partial \phi_0}{\partial \mathbf{n}_a} = 0 & \text{on } \Gamma_a^f, \\ \frac{\partial \phi_0}{\partial \mathbf{n}_a} = -\mathbf{v}_a^s \cdot \mathbf{n}_a & \text{on } \Gamma_a^b, \\ \frac{\partial \phi_0}{\partial \mathbf{n}_a} = -\mathbf{v}^{ap} \cdot \mathbf{n}_a & \text{on } \Gamma_a^r, \\ \operatorname{grad}_a \phi_0 = \mathbf{0} & \text{for } |z - o_a| \rightarrow \infty. \end{array} \right. \quad (9)$$

Consequently, the underlying velocity is

$$\mathbf{d}_a = \text{grad}_a \varphi_0 = \text{grad}_a \phi_0 + \mathbf{v}_a^s.$$

Notice that problem (9) does not involve any convective term and therefore an accurate discretization of this problem does not require any upwinding method. Moreover, in absence of transport phenomena in this model, the decay of the Laplacian solution ϕ_0 avoids the use of large computational domains. Hence, no severe spurious errors are involved in its numerical approximation, even in the case of truncating the unbounded domain \mathcal{A} at a small finite distance of the floating body.

4 Linear approximation

Since the motion X_f has been assumed as a small perturbation Y_f from the underlying motion Z_f , a linear model can be used to approximate the velocity potential φ_a . Associated with Y_f in (7), the linear model is obtained by applying a dimensional analysis to the equations in (7) and keeping only the first order terms with respect to a small parameter.

The typical value of the displacement perturbation (which is closely related with the magnitude of the oscillations of the free surface of the fluid) and the length of the floating body are denoted by H and L , respectively. Besides, the typical value of the apparent velocity of the underlying motion (more precisely, the subtraction of the stream and the rigid floating body velocities) is denoted by V . Then, L/V is the typical time the fluid takes to travel along the floating body. Accordingly, the following non-dimensional variables are introduced:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{t} &= \frac{V}{L} t, & \tilde{z} - o_a &= \frac{1}{L} (z - o_a), & \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_a^r &= \frac{1}{V} \mathbf{v}_a^r, & \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_a^s &= \frac{1}{V} \mathbf{v}_a^s, & \tilde{Y}_{f3} &= \frac{1}{L} Y_{f3}, \\ \tilde{\mathbf{d}}_a &= \frac{1}{V} \mathbf{d}_a, & \tilde{\mathbf{u}} &= \frac{1}{H} \mathbf{u}, & \tilde{\varphi}_a &= \frac{1}{VL} \varphi_a, & \tilde{\pi}_a &= \frac{L}{\rho_f V^2 L} \pi_a. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, once the second equation of model (7) is rewritten in terms of the displacement \mathbf{u} (notice $\frac{\partial Y_f}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial \tilde{t}}$) the non-dimensional version of (7) is given by

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \widetilde{\text{div}}_a \left(\det(\tilde{\mathbf{F}}_{Y_f}) \tilde{\mathbf{F}}_{Y_f}^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{F}}_{Y_f}^{-t} \widetilde{\text{grad}}_a \tilde{\varphi}_a \right) = 0 & \text{in } \tilde{\mathcal{A}} \times \mathbb{R}^+, \\ \frac{VH}{L} \frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{u}}}{\partial \tilde{t}} = V \tilde{\mathbf{F}}_{Y_f}^{-t} \widetilde{\text{grad}}_a \tilde{\varphi}_a - V \tilde{\mathbf{F}}_{Y_f} \tilde{\mathbf{d}}_a & \text{in } \tilde{\mathcal{A}} \times \mathbb{R}^+, \\ -V \rho_f \left(\frac{VH}{L^2} \left(\widetilde{\text{grad}}_a \frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{u}}}{\partial \tilde{t}} \right)^t + \frac{VH}{L^2} \left(\widetilde{\text{grad}}_a (\widetilde{\text{grad}}_a \tilde{\mathbf{u}})^t \right) \tilde{\mathbf{d}}_a \right) \tilde{\mathbf{F}}_{Y_f}^{-t} \widetilde{\text{grad}}_a \tilde{\varphi}_a \\ + \frac{V^2}{L} \rho_f \widetilde{\text{grad}}_a \widetilde{\text{grad}}_a \tilde{\varphi}_a \tilde{\mathbf{d}}_a + \frac{1}{L} \widetilde{\text{grad}}_a \left(V^2 \rho_f \frac{\partial \tilde{\varphi}_a}{\partial \tilde{t}} + V^2 \rho_f \tilde{\pi}_a + L \rho_f g \tilde{Y}_{f3} \right) = 0 & \text{in } \tilde{\mathcal{A}} \times \mathbb{R}^+, \\ V \tilde{\mathbf{F}}_{Y_f}^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{F}}_{Y_f}^{-t} \widetilde{\text{grad}}_a \tilde{\varphi}_a \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{n}}_a = V \tilde{\mathbf{F}}_{Y_f}^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_a^r \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{n}}_a & \text{on } \tilde{\Gamma}_a^r \times \mathbb{R}^+, \\ V \tilde{\mathbf{F}}_{Y_f}^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{F}}_{Y_f}^{-t} \widetilde{\text{grad}}_a \tilde{\varphi}_a \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{n}}_a = 0 & \text{on } \tilde{\Gamma}_a^b \times \mathbb{R}^+, \\ V \tilde{\mathbf{F}}_{Y_f}^{-t} \widetilde{\text{grad}}_a \tilde{\varphi}_a = V \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_a^s & \text{for } |\tilde{z} - o_a| \rightarrow \infty, \tilde{t} > 0, \end{array} \right. \quad (10)$$

where $\widetilde{\cdot}$ denotes non-dimensional differential operators and fields. Since $H \ll L$ in typical naval architecture applications (see [New99]), it is assumed that $\epsilon = \frac{H}{L}$ is a small parameter. Consequently, the tensor field $\tilde{\mathbf{F}}_{Y_f} = \mathbf{I} + \frac{H}{L} \widetilde{\text{grad}}_a \tilde{\mathbf{u}}$ and the Bernoulli equation (third equation in (10)) can be rewritten as

$$\mathbf{F}_{Y_f} = \mathbf{I} + O(\epsilon)$$

and

$$\rho_f \mathbf{grad}_a \text{grad}_a \varphi_a \mathbf{d}_a + \text{grad}_a \left(\rho_f \frac{\partial \varphi_a}{\partial t} + \pi_a + \rho_f g Y_{f3} \right) + O(\epsilon) = 0,$$

respectively. Thus, the linear approximation of the equations written above in their dimensional form are given by

$$\mathbf{F}_{Y_f} = \mathbf{I} \quad \text{in } \mathcal{A} \times \mathbb{R}^+, \quad (11)$$

$$\rho_f \mathbf{grad}_a \text{grad}_a \varphi_a \mathbf{d}_a + \text{grad}_a \left(\rho_f \frac{\partial \varphi_a}{\partial t} + \pi_a + \rho_f g Y_{f3} \right) = 0 \quad \text{in } \mathcal{A} \times \mathbb{R}^+. \quad (12)$$

Now, taking into account the linear approximations (11)-(12), a linearised model can be written from (7). For this purpose, \mathbf{F}_{Y_f} is approximated by \mathbf{I} in (10) unless in the second term of the right-hand side of the second equation in (7). Even in that case, if \mathbf{F}_{Y_f} is kept then the model is still linear. In addition, notice that if \mathbf{F}_{Y_f} was approximated by \mathbf{I} in all their occurrences then the Kelvin wave pattern would not be a solution of the linear model derived from (10). In conclusion, the following linear approximated

model is obtained:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \Delta_a \varphi_a = 0 & \text{in } \mathcal{A} \times \mathbb{R}^+, \\ \frac{\partial Y_f}{\partial t} = \text{grad}_a \varphi_a - \mathbf{grad}_a Y_f \mathbf{d}_a & \text{in } \mathcal{A} \times \mathbb{R}^+, \\ \rho_f \mathbf{grad}_a \text{grad}_a \varphi_a \mathbf{d}_a + \text{grad}_a \left(\rho_f \frac{\partial \varphi_a}{\partial t} + \pi_a + \rho_f g Y_{f3} \right) = 0 & \text{in } \mathcal{A} \times \mathbb{R}^+, \\ \frac{\partial \varphi_a}{\partial \mathbf{n}_a} = \mathbf{v}_a^r \cdot \mathbf{n}_a & \text{on } \Gamma_a^r \times \mathbb{R}^+, \\ \frac{\partial \varphi_a}{\partial \mathbf{n}_a} = 0 & \text{on } \Gamma_a^b \times \mathbb{R}^+, \\ \text{grad}_a \varphi_a = \mathbf{v}_a^s & \text{for } |z - o_a| \rightarrow \infty, t > 0, \end{array} \right. \quad (13)$$

where the velocity potential φ_a and the motion Y_f are the unknown fields to be computed, whereas \mathbf{d}_a is assumed known (computed from the solution ϕ_0 of the problem (9)).

5 Steady state

Now, once the AL description of the time-dependent hydrodynamic problem has been introduced in the previous section, model (13) will be solved at the steady state. In fact, since the main goal in this work consists in the numerical simulation of the Kelvin wakes and this phenomenon is assumed steady in the proposed AL framework. Hence, considering that velocities \mathbf{v}_a^s and \mathbf{v}_a^r are time independent, the steady state model is deduced from (13) by suppressing the terms which involve time derivatives. At the contrary of the classical hydrodynamic model, the system of equations (13) depends on the vector unknown Y_f and the scalar unknown φ_a . To reduce those unknowns in the steady state model and to consider only one scalar unknown field, the second equation in (13) is multiplied by the outward unit normal vector to the free surface in the AL configuration (for simplicity, it is assumed to be the third vector of the standard Cartesian basis in the AL coordinates system). Hence, it is obtained that

$$\text{grad}_a Y_f \mathbf{d}_a \cdot \mathbf{g}_3 = \text{grad}_a \varphi_a \cdot \mathbf{g}_3 \quad \text{in } \mathcal{A} \times \mathbb{R}^+$$

and since $\text{grad}_a Y_f \mathbf{d}_a \cdot \mathbf{g}_3 = \mathbf{d}_a \cdot (\text{grad}_a Y_f)^t \mathbf{g}_3 = \mathbf{d}_a \cdot \text{grad}_a (Y_f \cdot \mathbf{g}_3)$, then

$$\text{grad}_a \varphi_a \cdot \mathbf{g}_3 = \text{grad}_a Y_{f3} \cdot \mathbf{d}_a \quad \text{in } \mathcal{A} \times \mathbb{R}^+. \quad (14)$$

Similarly, the third equation of model (13) is multiplied by \mathbf{d}_a to get

$$\rho_f \mathbf{grad}_a \text{grad}_a \varphi_a \mathbf{d}_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a + \text{grad}(\pi_a + \rho_f g Y_{f3}) \cdot \mathbf{d}_a = 0 \quad \text{in } \mathcal{A} \times \mathbb{R}^+$$

and taking into account (14), it leads to

$$\rho_f \mathbf{grad}_a \text{grad}_a \varphi_a \mathbf{d}_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a + \text{grad} \pi_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a + \rho_f g \text{grad}_a \varphi_a \cdot \mathbf{g}_3 = 0 \quad \text{in } \mathcal{A} \times \mathbb{R}^+. \quad (15)$$

On the free surface Γ_a^f , the pressure π_a is supposed to be spatially homogeneous (usually equal to the atmospheric pressure). Since the outward unit normal vector to Γ_a^f is $\mathbf{n}_a = \mathbf{g}_3$ and \mathbf{d}_a is tangent to the free surface then $\mathbf{d}_a \cdot \mathbf{g}_3 = 0$. Hence, $\text{grad}_a \pi_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a = 0$ on Γ_a^f . Therefore, restricted to the free boundary, Equation (15) yields to the boundary condition

$$\frac{\partial \varphi_a}{\partial \mathbf{n}_a} = -\frac{1}{g} \mathbf{grad}_a \text{grad}_a \varphi_a \mathbf{d}_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a \quad \text{on } \Gamma_a^f.$$

Keeping in mind the radiation condition, the potential φ_a is decomposed using the same procedure applied for computing the underlying motion (see the decomposition for φ_0 described in Sect. 3) as $\varphi_a = \mathbf{v}_a^s \cdot (z - o_a) + \phi_a$. The normal derivative of ϕ_a can be written in terms of φ_a as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \phi_a}{\partial \mathbf{n}_a} = \frac{\partial \varphi_a}{\partial \mathbf{n}_a} - \mathbf{v}_a^s \cdot \mathbf{n}_a.$$

Since \mathbf{v}_a^s is tangent to the free surface boundary, then $\mathbf{v}_a^s \cdot \mathbf{n}_a = 0$ on Γ_a^f , and it is spatially constant then

$$\frac{\partial \phi_a}{\partial \mathbf{n}_a} = -\frac{1}{g} \mathbf{grad}_a \text{grad}_a \phi_a \mathbf{d}_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a \quad \text{on } \Gamma_a^f.$$

Additionally, the equation written above is equivalent to

$$\frac{\partial \phi_a}{\partial \mathbf{n}_a} = -\frac{1}{g} \text{grad}_a (\text{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a) \cdot \mathbf{d}_a + \frac{1}{g} \text{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{grad}_a \mathbf{d}_a \mathbf{d}_a \quad \text{on } \Gamma_a^f. \quad (16)$$

In conclusion, the AL formulation (13) of the steady-state model is given by

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \Delta_a \phi_a = 0 & \text{in } \mathcal{A}, \\ \frac{\partial \phi_a}{\partial \mathbf{n}_a} = -\frac{1}{g} \text{grad}_a (\text{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a) \cdot \mathbf{d}_a + \frac{1}{g} \text{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{grad}_a \mathbf{d}_a \mathbf{d}_a & \text{on } \Gamma_a^f, \\ \frac{\partial \phi_a}{\partial \mathbf{n}_a} = -\mathbf{v}^{ap} \cdot \mathbf{n}_a & \text{on } \Gamma_a^r, \\ \frac{\partial \phi_a}{\partial \mathbf{n}_a} = -\mathbf{v}_a^s \cdot \mathbf{n}_a & \text{on } \Gamma_a^b, \\ \text{grad}_a \phi_a = 0 & \text{for } |z - o_a| \rightarrow \infty, \end{array} \right. \quad (17)$$

where recall that $\mathbf{v}^{ap} = \mathbf{v}_a^s - \mathbf{v}_a^r$ is the apparent velocity of the fluid flow with respect to the velocity of the floating body.

Remark 5.1. Notice that the present model is a generalization of the classical one that can be found in the bibliography (see, for instance, [New99]) which has been widely used to compute Kelvin wake patterns (see for instance in [GMHF15]). The difference with the model introduced in (17) is located in the free surface boundary condition. Indeed, since \mathbf{v}^{ap} is constant, replacing \mathbf{d}_a by \mathbf{v}^{ap} in the free boundary condition of (16) leads to

$$\frac{\partial \phi_a}{\partial \mathbf{n}_a} = -\frac{1}{g} \text{grad}_a (\text{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{v}^{ap}) \cdot \mathbf{v}^{ap} \quad \text{on } \Gamma_a^f, \quad (18)$$

which is an equivalent writing of the free boundary condition in the classical linear model.

From a weak formulation point of view, model (17) could lead to an ill-posed variational problem stated in standard Sobolev spaces, since it involves a second order differential operator applied on the free surface Γ_a^f . However, since \mathbf{d}_a is a tangential vector to Γ_a^f , the trace $\text{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a$ can be defined for $\phi_a \in H^1(\mathcal{A})$ and an analogous argument can be applied to $\text{grad}_a (\text{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a) \cdot \mathbf{d}_a$ as far as $\text{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a \in H^1(\mathcal{A})$. Moreover, the second term on the right-hand side of the free boundary condition makes sense for $\phi_a \in H^1(\mathcal{A})$ because $\mathbf{grad}_a \mathbf{d}_a \mathbf{d}_a$ is also a tangential vector to Γ_a^f .

Consequently, to enforce that $\text{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a$ belongs to $H^1(\mathcal{A})$, a new unknown β is introduced in model (17), which is defined by $\beta = \text{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a$. Thus, problem (17) is written including the scalar field β as follows:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \Delta_a \phi_a = 0 & \text{in } \mathcal{A}, \\ \beta = \text{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a & \text{in } \mathcal{A}, \\ \frac{\partial \phi_a}{\partial \mathbf{n}_a} = -\frac{1}{g} \text{grad}_a \beta \cdot \mathbf{d}_a + \frac{1}{g} \text{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{grad}_a \mathbf{d}_a \mathbf{d}_a & \text{on } \Gamma_a^f, \\ \frac{\partial \phi_a}{\partial \mathbf{n}_a} = -\mathbf{v}^{ap} \cdot \mathbf{n}_a & \text{on } \Gamma_a^r, \\ \frac{\partial \phi_a}{\partial \mathbf{n}_a} = -\mathbf{v}_a^s \cdot \mathbf{n}_a & \text{on } \Gamma_a^b, \\ \text{grad}_a \phi_a = 0 & \text{for } |z - o_a| \rightarrow \infty. \end{array} \right. \quad (19)$$

6 Numerical resolution

In this section the numerical resolution of the steady problem (19) is discussed. With this purpose, the transport term $\text{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a$ should be discretized adequately and the unbounded domain \mathcal{A} must to be truncated taking into account the radiation condition. On one hand, since problem (19) is discretized by using a standard finite element procedure, the transport term must be treated conveniently by applying an upwinding methodology. On the other hand, a Perfectly Matched Layer technique is introduced to handle the radiation condition and truncate the unbounded domain \mathcal{A} .

In order to discretize the transport term properly, the second equation of (19) will be rewritten. The proposed upwinding strategy is described in Sect. 6.1. This methodology is inspired on the Streamline Upwind Petrov-Galerkin (SUPG) method. In fact, it has been derived because the straightforward application of the standard SUPG method produces spurious numerical oscillations when it is combined with the PML technique. Once the bounded computational domain has been described after introducing the PML layer in the original problem (19), then the weak form associated with the resulting system will be written.

6.1 Upwind methodology for handling the transport term

The SUPG method (see [BH82]) can be understood as an exchange of the continuous weighting functions for discontinuous ones in the Petrov-Galerkin discretization. Instead of working at the discrete finite element level, firstly an equivalent upwinding continuous problem can be introduced and then a standard Galerkin method is applied directly.

With the aim of describing the upwinding strategy, this procedure is derived from the second equation of problem (19) stated in an arbitrary domain \mathcal{D} , this is,

$$\beta = \text{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a \text{ in } \mathcal{D}.$$

Now, assume for a moment that φ_a is given in $H^1(\mathcal{D})$. The standard weak formulation of this equation is

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Find } \beta \in L^2(\mathcal{D}) \text{ such that} \\ \int_{\mathcal{D}} \beta \xi \, dV_x = \int_{\mathcal{D}} \text{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a \xi \, dV_x, \quad \forall \xi \in L^2(\mathcal{D}). \end{array} \right.$$

The modification of the test functions corresponding to the standard SUPG strategy consists in the substitution of ψ in the weak formulation above by

$$\xi^{SUPG} := \xi + k \text{grad}_a \xi \cdot \mathbf{d}_a, \quad (20)$$

where k is a constant which depends on the mesh size and the magnitude of the underlying velocity \mathbf{d}_a (see [BH82]). To ensure that $\xi^{SUPG} \in L^2(\mathcal{D})$, it is necessary to impose $\xi \in H^1(\mathcal{D})$. In fact, since the boundary conditions do not play any relevant role in this general description of the upwinding methodology, for simplicity it is assumed $\xi \in H_0^1(\mathcal{D})$. The corresponding weak formulation is given by

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Find } \beta \in L^2(\mathcal{D}) \text{ such that} \\ \int_{\mathcal{D}} \beta \xi^{SUPG} \, dV_x = \int_{\mathcal{D}} \text{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a \xi^{SUPG} \, dV_x, \quad \forall \xi \in H_0^1(\mathcal{D}). \end{array} \right.$$

Analogously, it can be assumed $\beta \in H^1(\mathcal{D})$ and hence, using (20) and a classical Green's formula, the previous weak formulation can be rewritten as follows:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Find } \beta \in H^1(\mathcal{D}) \text{ such that} \\ \int_{\mathcal{D}} \beta \xi dV_x - \int_{\mathcal{D}} \operatorname{div}_a(k\beta \mathbf{d}_a) \xi dV_x = \int_{\mathcal{D}} \operatorname{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a \xi dV_x - \int_{\mathcal{D}} \operatorname{div}_a(k \operatorname{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a \mathbf{d}_a) \xi dV_x, \quad \forall \xi \in H_0^1(\mathcal{D}). \end{array} \right.$$

This is a standard Galerkin weak formulation which leads to the strong equation

$$\beta - \operatorname{div}(k\beta \mathbf{d}_a) = \operatorname{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a - \operatorname{div}(k \operatorname{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a \mathbf{d}_a) \text{ in } \mathcal{D}.$$

Finally, since \mathbf{d}_a is divergence-free (\mathbf{d}_a is the underlying velocity field of an incompressible fluid), then

$$\beta - \mathbf{d}_a \cdot \operatorname{grad}_a(k\beta) = \operatorname{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a - \mathbf{d}_a \cdot \operatorname{grad}_a(k \operatorname{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a) \text{ in } \mathcal{D}. \quad (21)$$

This strategy was also used in the numerical resolution of the classical model (introduced in Remark 5.1).

In order to subsequently achieve an upwind discretization, the second equation in (19) is replaced by (21) with $k := h_d \delta_{\text{SUPG}} \frac{1}{|\mathbf{d}_a|}$, where $0 \leq \delta_{\text{SUPG}} \leq 1$ is a constant to be chosen (throughout the entire work, it has been fixed to $\delta_{\text{SUPG}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$ as [GMHF15] propose for a similar problem), and h_d is the cell diameter of the finite element mesh.

In conclusion, the modified steady-state problem to be solved is given by

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \Delta_a \phi_a = 0 & \text{in } \mathcal{A}, \\ \beta - \mathbf{d}_a \cdot \operatorname{grad}_a(k\beta) = \operatorname{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a - \mathbf{d}_a \cdot \operatorname{grad}_a(k \operatorname{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a) & \text{in } \mathcal{A}, \\ \frac{\partial \phi_a}{\partial \mathbf{n}_a} = -\frac{1}{g} \operatorname{grad}_a \beta \cdot \mathbf{d}_a + \frac{1}{g} \operatorname{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{grad}_a \mathbf{d}_a \mathbf{d}_a & \text{on } \Gamma_a^f, \\ \frac{\partial \phi_a}{\partial \mathbf{n}_a} = -\mathbf{v}^{ap} \cdot \mathbf{n}_a & \text{on } \Gamma_a^r, \\ \frac{\partial \phi_a}{\partial \mathbf{n}_a} = -\mathbf{v}_a^s \cdot \mathbf{n}_a & \text{on } \Gamma_a^b, \\ \operatorname{grad}_a \phi_a = 0 & \text{for } |z - o_a| \rightarrow \infty. \end{array} \right. \quad (22)$$

At this point, it should be emphasized that this methodology provides a general approach for upwinding convective term discretizations, which is suitable to combine with the use of PML methods to truncate the original unbounded domain.

6.2 Perfectly Matched Layer technique

Before the discretization of problem (22), the unbounded domain \mathcal{A} must be truncated and the radiation condition (see the last equation of problem (22)) must be taken into account. Both tasks are being addressed with the use of an adequate PML layer. Since the fluid domain is only assumed unbounded in the horizontal spatial coordinates, the computational domain will be truncated using a cylindrical surface. Thus, the bounded computational domain is composed by two subdomains: the truncated fluid domain \mathcal{A}_F (where the fluid around the floating body is located), and an exterior cylindrical annulus \mathcal{A}_∞ (where the PML governing equations are stated). This truncation process is determined by two parameters: the inner and outer radius of the annulus, this is, the radius of the fluid domain R and the outer radius of the cylindrical annulus R_∞ . In this manner, both computational subdomains are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}_F &= \{z = (z_1, z_2, z_3) \in \mathcal{A} : z_1^2 + z_2^2 < R^2\}, \\ \mathcal{A}_\infty &= \{z = (z_1, z_2, z_3) \in \mathcal{A} : R^2 < z_1^2 + z_2^2 < R_\infty^2\}. \end{aligned}$$

The coupling boundary between both subdomains is given by $\partial \mathcal{A}^i = \partial \mathcal{A}_F \cap \partial \mathcal{A}_\infty$. Additionally, the disjoint splitting of the boundaries in \mathcal{A} is also kept in the fluid and PML subdomains. Consequently, a new set of boundaries are introduced:

- (a) the boundaries associated with the fluid subdomain are the free surface, $\partial \mathcal{A}^f$, the seabed, $\partial \mathcal{A}^b$, and the wet surface of the floating body, $\partial \mathcal{A}^r$, which are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \partial \mathcal{A}^f &= \{z = (z_1, z_2, z_3) \in \partial \mathcal{A}_F : z_3 = 0\}, \\ \partial \mathcal{A}^b &= \partial \mathcal{A}_F \cap \Gamma_a^b, \\ \partial \mathcal{A}^r &= \Gamma_a^r, \end{aligned}$$

- (b) the boundaries corresponding to the PML are the free surface, $\partial \mathcal{A}_\infty^f$, the seabed, $\partial \mathcal{A}_\infty^b$ and the outer vertical boundary of the PML subdomain, $\partial \mathcal{A}_\infty^\infty$. They are defined by

$$\begin{aligned} \partial \mathcal{A}_\infty^f &= \{z = (z_1, z_2, z_3) \in \partial \mathcal{A}_\infty : z_3 = 0\}, \\ \partial \mathcal{A}_\infty^b &= \partial \mathcal{A}_\infty \cap \Gamma_a^b, \\ \partial \mathcal{A}_\infty^\infty &= \{z = (z_1, z_2, z_3) \in \partial \mathcal{A}_\infty : z_1^2 + z_2^2 = R_\infty^2\}. \end{aligned}$$

Remark 6.1. *The fluid domain \mathcal{A} is originally assumed with a finite depth and hence, no truncation procedures must be applied in the vertical spatial direction. Otherwise, if a infinite depth is considered, then the velocity potential in problem (22) would exhibit an exponential decay behaviour with respect to the coordinate z_3 and a PML layer of Laplacian type (see [Tre09]) should be used to truncate the unbounded domain in the z_3 -axis. Anyway, in both cases (with finite or infinite depth), the PML technique stated on the cylindrical annulus \mathcal{A}_∞ is required due to the presence of the convective term in the free surface condition (see the third equation in problem (22)).*

The PML technique (introduced in problem (22)) produces an adequate absorption of those waves associated with the Kelvin wake in the radial direction. Since problem (22) is a steady-state model involving a Laplacian equation, a straightforward approach could consider the use of a Laplacian-like PML (see [Tre09] for more details). However, that PML model cannot handle the transport effects arising from the convective term on the free surface condition. Consequently, despite the presence of the floating body generates a stationary wave (the so-called Kelvin wake pattern) a wave-like PML (typically for time-harmonic problems) has been considered. More precisely, the PML model analysed by [CI12] in a two-dimensional Cartesian setting for a hydrodynamic problem with constant underlying velocity has been extended for the proposed model (22) within a three-dimensional domain written in cylindrical coordinates.

Remark 6.2. *Since a time-harmonic PML model has been considered, a specific value for the angular frequency should be associated with the steady-state model (22). For this purpose, the Kelvin wake pattern can be approximated locally by a linear combination of plane waves propagating in a predominant direction which forms an angle θ_p with respect to the underlying velocity (see [New99] for a detailed discussion). Since the wave motion associated with the Kelvin wake is stationary (with respect to a reference configuration fixed on the floating body), these local plane wave of the form $e^{-i\omega t} e^{i\boldsymbol{\kappa} \cdot (z - o_a)}$ should be time-independent, this is, assuming that $z = p + \mathbf{v}^{\alpha p} t$, then*

$$\omega t - \boldsymbol{\kappa} \cdot (z - o_a) = (\omega - \boldsymbol{\kappa} \cdot \mathbf{v}^{\alpha p})t + p$$

should be independent of time, or equivalently, it holds $\omega = \|\boldsymbol{\kappa}\| \|\mathbf{v}^{\alpha p}\| \cos \theta_p$, where $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ denotes the wavenumber vector. Additionally, the dispersion relation for a plane wave propagated in fluid domain of finite depth d and a free surface boundary is given by $\omega^2 = g \|\boldsymbol{\kappa}\| \tanh(\|\boldsymbol{\kappa}\| d)$. Hence,

$$\omega = \frac{g}{\|\mathbf{v}^{\alpha p}\| \cos \theta_p} \tanh\left(\frac{\omega}{\|\mathbf{v}^{\alpha p}\| \cos \theta_p} d\right)$$

where the value of θ_p can be approximated by $\theta_p = 0.6155$ rad (see [New99] for a detailed derivation).

To derive the time-harmonic governing equations of a PML model acting as an absorber layer in the radial direction, firstly the linear problem (22) must be written in cylindrical coordinates (r, θ, z) associated with the Cartesian coordinates $z = (z_1, z_2, z_3)$ in the AL configuration. Then, taking into account the time-harmonic PML models can be understood as a complex-stretching of the spatial coordinates (see [CW94]), the radial coordinate r is formally replaced by a new complex-valued function \hat{r} , which introduces an artificial dissipation to damp the outgoing waves. The choice of function \hat{r} depends on the so-called absorption PML profile $\sigma_r : [R, R_\infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$, which is an increasing non-negative continuous function. For the sake of simplicity, it is assumed $\sigma_r(R) = 0$. In order to write the governing equations in the PML domain, some complex-valued expressions are introduced:

$$\hat{r}(r) := r + \frac{i}{\omega} \int_R^r \sigma_r(s) ds, \quad \sigma_\theta(r) := \frac{1}{r} \int_R^r \sigma_r(s) ds, \quad \gamma(r) := \frac{\partial \hat{r}}{\partial r}(r) = 1 + \frac{i}{\omega} \sigma_r(r), \quad \hat{\gamma}(r) := \frac{\hat{r}}{r}(r) = 1 + \frac{i}{\omega} \sigma_\theta(r).$$

If r is formally replaced by \hat{r} , and denoting the new gradient and divergence operators with $\widehat{\cdot}$, then the expressions of operators $\widehat{\text{grad}}_a$, $\widehat{\text{grad}}_a \mathbf{w}$ and $\widehat{\text{div}}_a$ in cylindrical coordinates are replaced by

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{\text{grad}}_a \phi &= \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \hat{r}} \mathbf{e}_r + \frac{1}{\hat{r}} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \theta} \mathbf{e}_\theta + \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial z} \mathbf{e}_z, \\ \widehat{\text{grad}}_a \mathbf{w} &= \frac{\partial w_r}{\partial \hat{r}} \mathbf{e}_r \otimes \mathbf{e}_r + \left[\frac{1}{\hat{r}} \frac{\partial w_r}{\partial \theta} - \frac{1}{\hat{r}} w_\theta \right] \mathbf{e}_r \otimes \mathbf{e}_\theta + \frac{\partial w_r}{\partial z} \mathbf{e}_r \otimes \mathbf{e}_z + \frac{\partial w_\theta}{\partial \hat{r}} \mathbf{e}_\theta \otimes \mathbf{e}_r + \left[\frac{1}{\hat{r}} \frac{\partial w_\theta}{\partial \theta} + \frac{1}{\hat{r}} w_r \right] \mathbf{e}_\theta \otimes \mathbf{e}_\theta + \frac{\partial w_\theta}{\partial z} \mathbf{e}_\theta \otimes \mathbf{e}_z \\ &\quad + \frac{\partial w_z}{\partial \hat{r}} \mathbf{e}_z \otimes \mathbf{e}_r + \frac{1}{\hat{r}} \frac{\partial w_z}{\partial \theta} \mathbf{e}_z \otimes \mathbf{e}_\theta + \frac{\partial w_z}{\partial z} \mathbf{e}_z \otimes \mathbf{e}_z, \\ \widehat{\text{div}}_a \mathbf{w} &= \frac{1}{\hat{r}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \hat{r}} (\hat{r} w_r) + \frac{1}{\hat{r}} \frac{\partial w_\theta}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial w_z}{\partial z}, \end{aligned}$$

where $\{\mathbf{e}_r, \mathbf{e}_\theta, \mathbf{e}_z\}$ is the orthonormal basis associated to this coordinate system. Replacing \hat{r} with $r\hat{\gamma}(r)$ it holds

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{\text{grad}}_a \phi &= \frac{1}{\gamma} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial r} \mathbf{e}_r + \frac{1}{\hat{\gamma} r} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \theta} \mathbf{e}_\theta + \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial z} \mathbf{e}_z = \mathbf{C} \text{grad}_a \phi, \\ \widehat{\text{grad}}_a \mathbf{w} &= \text{grad}_a \mathbf{w} (\mathbf{C} \mathbf{w}), \\ \widehat{\text{div}}_a \mathbf{w} &= \frac{1}{\hat{\gamma} \gamma r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r \hat{\gamma} w_r) + \frac{1}{\hat{\gamma} r} \frac{\partial w_\theta}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial w_z}{\partial z} = \frac{1}{\hat{\gamma} \gamma} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r \hat{\gamma} w_r) + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial w_\theta}{\partial \theta} (\gamma w_\theta) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (\gamma \hat{\gamma} w_z) \right) = \det(\mathbf{C}) \text{div}_a (\det(\mathbf{C})^{-1} \mathbf{C} \mathbf{w}), \end{aligned}$$

where \mathbf{C} is the PML tensor field, $\mathbf{C} := \frac{1}{\gamma} \mathbf{e}_r \otimes \mathbf{e}_r + \frac{1}{\hat{\gamma}} \mathbf{e}_\theta \otimes \mathbf{e}_\theta + \mathbf{e}_z \otimes \mathbf{e}_z$. Notice that \mathbf{C} is diagonal in the cylindrical reference system. Therefore,

$$\hat{\Delta}_a \hat{\phi}_a = \widehat{\text{div}}_a (\widehat{\text{grad}}_a \hat{\phi}_a) = \det(\mathbf{C}) \text{div}_a (\det(\mathbf{C})^{-1} \mathbf{C} \text{grad}_a \hat{\phi}_a) = \frac{1}{\hat{\gamma} \gamma} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{\hat{\gamma}}{\gamma} r \frac{\partial \hat{\phi}_a}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{\gamma}{\hat{\gamma}} \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 \hat{\phi}_a}{\partial \theta^2} + \gamma \hat{\gamma} \frac{\partial^2 \hat{\phi}_a}{\partial z^2} \right).$$

By an analogous procedure, the equation associated with the transport term can be obtained, namely,

$$\hat{\beta} - \mathbf{d}_a \cdot \widehat{\text{grad}}_a (k \hat{\beta}) = \widehat{\text{grad}}_a \hat{\phi}_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a - \mathbf{d}_a \cdot \widehat{\text{grad}}_a (k \widehat{\text{grad}}_a \hat{\phi}_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a) \text{ in } \mathcal{A}_\infty,$$

or, equivalently,

$$\hat{\beta} - \mathbf{d}_a \cdot \mathbf{C} \text{grad}_a(k\hat{\beta}) = \mathbf{C} \text{grad}_a \hat{\phi}_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a - \mathbf{d}_a \cdot \mathbf{C} \text{grad}_a \left(k \mathbf{C} \text{grad}_a \hat{\phi}_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a \right) \text{ in } \mathcal{A}_\infty, \quad (23)$$

which is a similar equation to the second equation in (22).

As the last step, the boundary conditions on the free surface of the PML have to be derived. Firstly, an analogous equation to the third equation in (22) can be written, as follows:

$$\widehat{\text{grad}}_a \hat{\phi}_a \cdot \mathbf{n}_\infty = -\frac{1}{g} \widehat{\text{grad}}_a \hat{\beta} \cdot \mathbf{d}_a + \frac{1}{g} \widehat{\text{grad}}_a \hat{\phi}_a \cdot \widehat{\mathbf{grad}}_a \mathbf{d}_a \mathbf{d}_a \text{ on } \partial \mathcal{A}_\infty^f,$$

which is equivalent to

$$\mathbf{C} \text{grad}_a \hat{\phi}_a \cdot \mathbf{n}_\infty = -\frac{1}{g} \mathbf{C} \text{grad}_a \hat{\beta} \cdot \mathbf{d}_a + \frac{1}{g} \mathbf{C} \text{grad}_a \hat{\phi}_a \cdot \mathbf{grad}_a \mathbf{d}_a (\mathbf{C} \mathbf{d}_a) \text{ on } \partial \mathcal{A}_\infty^f.$$

Since $\mathbf{n}_\infty = \mathbf{e}_3$ on $\partial \mathcal{A}_\infty^f$ then $\mathbf{n}_\infty = \mathbf{C} \mathbf{n}_\infty$, and so the above equation is also equivalent to

$$\det(\mathbf{C}^{-1}) \mathbf{C} \mathbf{C} \text{grad}_a \hat{\phi}_a \cdot \mathbf{n}_\infty = -\frac{1}{g} \det(\mathbf{C}^{-1}) \mathbf{C} \text{grad}_a \hat{\beta} \cdot \mathbf{d}_a + \frac{1}{g} \det(\mathbf{C}^{-1}) \mathbf{C} \text{grad}_a \hat{\phi}_a \cdot \mathbf{grad}_a \mathbf{d}_a (\mathbf{C} \mathbf{d}_a) \text{ on } \partial \mathcal{A}_\infty^f.$$

Similarly, the boundary condition on the seabed in the PML domain takes the form

$$\det(\mathbf{C}^{-1}) \mathbf{C} \mathbf{C} \text{grad}_a \hat{\phi}_a \cdot \mathbf{n}_\infty = -\det(\mathbf{C}^{-1}) \mathbf{v}_a^s \cdot \mathbf{n}_\infty \text{ on } \partial \mathcal{A}_\infty^b.$$

Finally, for the sake of simplicity the notation $\mathbf{S} := \det(\mathbf{C}^{-1}) \mathbf{C} \mathbf{C}$ is introduced. Since $\det(\mathbf{C}) \neq 0$ then the system of governing equations in the PML subdomain is

$$\begin{cases} \text{div}_a (\mathbf{S} \text{grad}_a \hat{\phi}_a) = 0 & \text{in } \mathcal{A}_\infty, \\ \hat{\beta} - \mathbf{d}_a \cdot \mathbf{C} \text{grad}_a(k\hat{\beta}) = \mathbf{C} \text{grad}_a \hat{\phi}_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a - \mathbf{d}_a \cdot \mathbf{C} \text{grad}_a \left(k \mathbf{C} \text{grad}_a \hat{\phi}_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a \right) & \text{in } \mathcal{A}_\infty, \\ \mathbf{S} \text{grad}_a \hat{\phi}_a \cdot \mathbf{n}_\infty = -\frac{1}{g} \det(\mathbf{C}^{-1}) \mathbf{C} \text{grad}_a \hat{\beta} \cdot \mathbf{d}_a + \frac{1}{g} \det(\mathbf{C}^{-1}) \mathbf{C} \text{grad}_a \hat{\phi}_a \cdot \mathbf{grad}_a \mathbf{d}_a (\mathbf{C} \mathbf{d}_a) & \text{on } \partial \mathcal{A}_\infty^f, \\ \mathbf{S} \text{grad}_a \hat{\phi}_a \cdot \mathbf{n}_\infty = -\det(\mathbf{C}^{-1}) \mathbf{v}_a^s \cdot \mathbf{n}_\infty & \text{on } \partial \mathcal{A}_\infty^b, \\ \hat{\phi}_a = 0 & \text{on } \partial \mathcal{A}^\infty, \\ \hat{\beta} = 0 & \text{on } \partial \mathcal{A}^\infty, \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

and in the fluid subdomain, it holds

$$\begin{cases} \Delta_a \phi_a = 0 & \text{in } \mathcal{A}_F, \\ \beta - \mathbf{d}_a \cdot \text{grad}_a(k\beta) = \text{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a - \mathbf{d}_a \cdot \text{grad}_a (k \text{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a) & \text{in } \mathcal{A}_F, \\ \frac{\partial \phi_a}{\partial \mathbf{n}_a} = -\frac{1}{g} \text{grad}_a \beta \cdot \mathbf{d}_a + \frac{1}{g} \text{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{grad}_a \mathbf{d}_a \mathbf{d}_a & \text{on } \partial \mathcal{A}^f, \\ \frac{\partial \phi_a}{\partial \mathbf{n}_a} = -\mathbf{v}^{ap} \cdot \mathbf{n}_a & \text{on } \partial \mathcal{A}^r, \\ \frac{\partial \phi_a}{\partial \mathbf{n}_a} = -\mathbf{v}_a^s \cdot \mathbf{n}_a & \text{on } \partial \mathcal{A}^b. \end{cases} \quad (25)$$

The unknown fields in the fluid and the PML subdomains are coupled by the transmission conditions

$$\begin{cases} \phi_a = \hat{\phi}_a & \text{on } \partial \mathcal{A}^i, \\ \frac{\partial \phi_a}{\partial \mathbf{n}_a} = -\mathbf{S} \text{grad}_a \hat{\phi}_a \cdot \mathbf{n}_\infty & \text{on } \partial \mathcal{A}^i, \\ \beta = \hat{\beta} & \text{on } \partial \mathcal{A}^i, \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

where $\mathbf{n}_\infty = -\mathbf{n}_a$ on $\partial \mathcal{A}^i$.

6.3 Weak formulation

Once the convective terms have been handled with an adequate upwinding strategy and the use of a cylindrical PML layer ensures an accurate damping of the outgoing waves in the truncated computational domain, the governing equations in the fluid and the PML subdomains must be written in a weak form. With this aim, a convenient functional space W must be introduced, where the unknown field pairs $(\phi_a, \hat{\phi}_a)$ and $(\beta, \hat{\beta})$ are sought. So, the functional space W is defined by

$$W := \{(u, \hat{u}) \in H^1(\mathcal{A}_F) \times H^1(\mathcal{A}_\infty) : u|_{\partial \mathcal{A}^i} = \hat{u}|_{\partial \mathcal{A}^i}, \hat{u}|_{\partial \mathcal{A}^\infty} = 0\}.$$

In order to obtain a weak formulation of the strong problem (24)-(26), test functions $(\psi, \hat{\psi}), (\xi, \hat{\xi}) \in W$ are considered. Before writing the weak formulation, it is necessary to define \mathcal{A}_U as the interior set of the closure of the union of the fluid subdomain with the PML subdomain, $\mathcal{A}_U := \text{Int}(\overline{\mathcal{A}_F \cup \mathcal{A}_\infty})$, to introduce the spaces corresponding to $\mathbf{d}_a \in (H^1(\mathcal{A}_U))^3$, and $k \in L^\infty(\mathcal{A}_U)$. Then, by applying standard procedures involving Green's formulas and using the boundary conditions of the problem (8) (assuming

$\Gamma_a^f = \partial\mathcal{A}^f \cup \partial\mathcal{A}_\infty^f$, $\Gamma_a^b = \partial\mathcal{A}^b \cup \partial\mathcal{A}_\infty^b$ and $\Gamma_a^r = \partial\mathcal{A}^r$) and some properties of the tensor \mathbf{C} (namely, its symmetry, $\mathbf{C}|_{\partial\mathcal{A}^i} = \mathbf{I}$ and $\mathbf{Cn}_\infty = \mathbf{n}_\infty$ on $\partial\mathcal{A}_\infty^f \cup \partial\mathcal{A}_\infty^b$), it is straightforward to get the following weak formulation:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Given } \mathbf{d}_a \in (H^1(\mathcal{A}_U))^3 \text{ and } k \in L^\infty(\mathcal{A}_U), \text{ find } (\phi_a, \hat{\phi}_a), (\beta, \hat{\beta}) \in W \text{ such that} \\ \int_{\mathcal{A}_F} \text{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \text{grad}_a \psi dV_x + \frac{1}{g} \int_{\partial\mathcal{A}^f} \text{grad}_a \beta \cdot \mathbf{d}_a \psi dA_x - \frac{1}{g} \int_{\partial\mathcal{A}^f} \text{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{grad}_a \mathbf{d}_a \psi dA_x \\ + \int_{\mathcal{A}_\infty} \mathbf{S} \text{grad}_a \hat{\phi}_a \cdot \text{grad}_a \hat{\psi} dV_x + \frac{1}{g} \int_{\partial\mathcal{A}_\infty^f} \det(\mathbf{C}^{-1}) \mathbf{C} \text{grad}_a \hat{\beta} \cdot \mathbf{d}_a \hat{\psi} dA_x \\ - \frac{1}{g} \int_{\partial\mathcal{A}_\infty^f} \det(\mathbf{C}^{-1}) \mathbf{C} \text{grad}_a \hat{\phi}_a \cdot \mathbf{grad}_a \mathbf{d}_a (\mathbf{C} \mathbf{d}_a) \hat{\psi} dA_x = - \int_{\partial\mathcal{A}^r} \mathbf{v}^{ap} \cdot \mathbf{n}_a \psi dA_x - \int_{\partial\mathcal{A}^b} \mathbf{v}_a^s \cdot \mathbf{n}_a \psi dA_x \\ - \int_{\partial\mathcal{A}_\infty^b} \det(\mathbf{C}^{-1}) \mathbf{v}_a^s \cdot \mathbf{n}_\infty \hat{\psi} dA_x \quad \forall (\psi, \hat{\psi}) \in W, \\ \int_{\mathcal{A}_F} \beta \xi dV_x + \int_{\mathcal{A}_F} k \beta \mathbf{d}_a \cdot \text{grad}_a \xi dV_x - \int_{\partial\mathcal{A}^r} k \beta \mathbf{v}_a^r \cdot \mathbf{n}_a \xi dA_x - \int_{\mathcal{A}_F} \text{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a \xi dV_x \\ - \int_{\mathcal{A}_F} k \text{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a \mathbf{d}_a \cdot \text{grad}_a \xi dV_x + \int_{\partial\mathcal{A}^r} k \text{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a \mathbf{v}_a^r \cdot \mathbf{n}_a \xi dA_x \\ + \int_{\mathcal{A}_\infty} \hat{\beta} \hat{\xi} dV_x + \int_{\mathcal{A}_\infty} k \hat{\beta} \text{div}(\mathbf{C} \mathbf{d}_a \hat{\xi}) dV_x - \int_{\mathcal{A}_\infty} \mathbf{C} \text{grad}_a \hat{\phi}_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a \hat{\xi} dV_x \\ - \int_{\mathcal{A}_\infty} k \mathbf{C} \text{grad}_a \hat{\phi}_a \cdot \mathbf{d}_a \text{div}(\mathbf{C} \mathbf{d}_a \hat{\xi}) dV_x = 0 \quad \forall (\xi, \hat{\xi}) \in W. \end{array} \right. \quad (27)$$

Remark 6.3. The underlying velocity \mathbf{d}_a is computed from the approximation of the solution of (9), $\mathbf{d}_a = \text{grad}_a \phi_0 + \mathbf{v}_a^s$, plus a projection in the vectorial Sobolev space $(H^1(\mathcal{A}_U))^3$. As mentioned in the Sect. 3, the numerical resolution of the system (9) can avoid the use of large computational domains. Then, the solution $\phi_0 \in H^1(\mathcal{A}_U)$ can be approximated without using the PML technique, with the same mesh taking the PML subdomain as fluid domain, and imposing a null Dirichlet condition in the outer vertical boundary of the PML subdomain ($\partial\mathcal{A}^\infty$).

6.4 Discrete space

The discretization of the weak form (27) is based on a standard finite element method associated with a compatible tetrahedral mesh \mathcal{T}_F^h and \mathcal{T}_∞^h of the domains \mathcal{A}_F and \mathcal{A}_∞ , respectively. Let $X^h(\mathcal{A}_U) \subset H^1(\mathcal{A}_U)$, be the standard discrete space consisting of continuous piecewise linear functions and $W^h = \{(u, \hat{u}) \in W : u \in X^h(\mathcal{A}_F), \hat{u} \in X^h(\mathcal{A}_\infty)\} \subset W$. Let $Y^h \subset L^\infty(\mathcal{A}_U)$ be the discrete space of piecewise constant functions. Then, the discrete variational formulation is described as follows:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Given } \mathbf{d}_a^h \in (X^h(\mathcal{A}_U))^3 \text{ and } k^h \in Y^h, \text{ find } (\phi_a^h, \hat{\phi}_a^h), (\beta^h, \hat{\beta}^h) \in W^h \text{ such that} \\ \int_{\mathcal{A}_F} \text{grad}_a \phi_a^h \cdot \text{grad}_a \psi^h dV_x + \frac{1}{g} \int_{\partial\mathcal{A}^f} \text{grad}_a \beta^h \cdot \mathbf{d}_a^h \psi^h dA_x - \frac{1}{g} \int_{\partial\mathcal{A}^f} \text{grad}_a \phi_a^h \cdot \mathbf{grad}_a \mathbf{d}_a^h \psi^h dA_x \\ + \int_{\mathcal{A}_\infty} \mathbf{S} \text{grad}_a \hat{\phi}_a^h \cdot \text{grad}_a \hat{\psi}^h dV_x + \frac{1}{g} \int_{\partial\mathcal{A}_\infty^f} \det(\mathbf{C}^{-1}) \mathbf{C} \text{grad}_a \hat{\beta}^h \cdot \mathbf{d}_a^h \hat{\psi}^h dA_x \\ - \frac{1}{g} \int_{\partial\mathcal{A}_\infty^f} \det(\mathbf{C}^{-1}) \mathbf{C} \text{grad}_a \hat{\phi}_a^h \cdot \mathbf{grad}_a \mathbf{d}_a^h (\mathbf{C} \mathbf{d}_a^h) \hat{\psi}^h dA_x = - \int_{\partial\mathcal{A}^r} \mathbf{v}^{ap} \cdot \mathbf{n}_a \psi^h dA_x - \int_{\partial\mathcal{A}^b} \mathbf{v}_a^s \cdot \mathbf{n}_a \psi^h dA_x \\ - \int_{\partial\mathcal{A}_\infty^b} \det(\mathbf{C}^{-1}) \mathbf{v}_a^s \cdot \mathbf{n}_\infty \hat{\psi}^h dA_x \quad \forall (\psi^h, \hat{\psi}^h) \in W^h, \\ \int_{\mathcal{A}_F} \beta^h \xi^h dV_x + \int_{\mathcal{A}_F} k^h \beta^h \mathbf{d}_a^h \cdot \text{grad}_a \xi^h dV_x - \int_{\partial\mathcal{A}^r} k^h \beta^h \mathbf{v}_a^r \cdot \mathbf{n}_a \xi^h dA_x - \int_{\mathcal{A}_F} \text{grad}_a \phi_a^h \cdot \mathbf{d}_a^h \xi^h dV_x \\ - \int_{\mathcal{A}_F} k^h \text{grad}_a \phi_a^h \cdot \mathbf{d}_a^h \mathbf{d}_a^h \cdot \text{grad}_a \xi^h dV_x + \int_{\partial\mathcal{A}^r} k^h \text{grad}_a \phi_a^h \cdot \mathbf{d}_a^h \mathbf{v}_a^r \cdot \mathbf{n}_a \xi^h dA_x \\ + \int_{\mathcal{A}_\infty} \hat{\beta}^h \hat{\xi}^h dV_x + \int_{\mathcal{A}_\infty} k^h \hat{\beta}^h \text{div}(\mathbf{C} \mathbf{d}_a^h \hat{\xi}^h) dV_x - \int_{\mathcal{A}_\infty} \mathbf{C} \text{grad}_a \hat{\phi}_a^h \cdot \mathbf{d}_a^h \hat{\xi}^h dV_x \\ - \int_{\mathcal{A}_\infty} k^h \mathbf{C} \text{grad}_a \hat{\phi}_a^h \cdot \mathbf{d}_a^h \text{div}(\mathbf{C} \mathbf{d}_a^h \hat{\xi}^h) dV_x = 0 \quad \forall (\xi^h, \hat{\xi}^h) \in W^h. \end{array} \right.$$

Remark 6.4. The function k is a measure of the size of each element, thus, it is constant function per element and can be represented as a function in the discrete space Y^h . Moreover, the underlying velocity $\mathbf{d}_a = \text{grad}_a \phi_0 + \mathbf{v}_a^s$ was computed from the approximated solution ϕ_0^h of the problem (9), by means of $\mathbf{d}_a^h = \Pi_h(\text{grad}_a \phi_0^h) + \mathbf{v}_a^s$, where Π_h is the L^2 -projection into the discrete space $X^h(\mathcal{A}_U)^3$ (see Remark 6.3).

7 Numerical results

In this section the numerical simulation of the steady motion of the fluid produced by the movement of a floating body is described in detail. First, a brief description of the geometry is introduced and the meshes used in the numerical experiments are shown. Second, a preliminary study of the accuracy of the PML is performed. Third, the numerical results of the proposed approach are compared with respect to those ones obtained with the classical linear model presented in [New99] and used in [GMHF15]. Moreover, the same test problem has been modelled by a turbulent k - ω model coupled with the full Navier-Stokes equations considering the free

Figure 3: Surface of the Wigley hull on the left, with 2.5 m waterline length, 0.25 m beam at midship and 0.156 m depth at midship. Computational domain of 2.35 meters of depth, on the right, consisting in a fluid subdomain with a radius of two meters (highlighted in green) and PML cylindrical annular subdomain with a thickness of one meter (highlighted in yellow).

surface as the interface between two species: air and water (solved with a widely used commercial software: Ansys Fluent). The three kinds of numerical results have been compared with respect to available experimental data (see [KMI⁺83]). Finally, the effect of the finite element discretization on the accuracy of the numerical results is analysed by comparing the proposed linear model and the classical in a variety of scenarios: considering different underlying velocities, using either a finer mesh on the wet surface of the floating body or a finer mesh on the free surface of the fluid domain. The results shown below have been obtained with a computational code written in Python, where the FEniCS library (see [ABH⁺15] and [LMW⁺12]) has been used.

7.1 Wigley hull. Experimental data

The Wigley hull is a geometry commonly used as benchmark in hydrodynamic simulations due to experimental data from the bibliography (see, for instance, [KMI⁺83]). The shape of the Wigley hull has an analytic expression: a point $(x, y, z) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ belongs to the Wigley hull if and only if

$$y = \frac{B_w}{2} \left(1 - \left(\frac{2x}{L_w} \right)^2 \right) \left(1 - \left(\frac{z}{D_w} \right)^2 \right) \quad x \in \left[-\frac{L_w}{2}, \frac{L_w}{2} \right] \quad \text{and} \quad z \in [-D_w, 0], \quad (28)$$

where B_w denotes the beam at midship, L_w the waterline length and D_w the draft at midship; throughout all the numerical simulations, $B_w = 0.25$, $L_w = 2.5$ and $D_w = 0.156$. Since this hull is symmetric with respect to the XZ -plane then its symmetry has been considered in the numerical simulation.

Taking into account the symmetry of this computational domain and assuming that the apparent and stream velocity are parallel to the longitudinal axis of the Wigley hull, the solution of the weak problem is symmetric with respect to its axis and hence only the half of the computational domain is considered, imposing an homogeneous Neumann condition on the plane of symmetry.

The available Wigley experimental data has been obtained from [KMI⁺83], where the experiments involve a Wigley hull in motion aligned with its main edge at different apparent velocities. To reproduce numerically the experimental data, different Froude numbers, $\text{Fr} := \frac{|\mathbf{v}_a^r|}{\sqrt{gL_w}}$ has been considered, more precisely, $\text{Fr} = 0.25, 0.267, 0.289, 0.316, 0.354, 0.408$.

All the numerical simulations with PML shown in this work involve a fluid domain with 2 meters radius and a PML with 1 meter thick and 2.35 meters depth (see Fig. 3, left). The dimensions of the hull and the depth correspond to the experiments reported in [KMI⁺83].

Two different meshes were considered in this work (see Figs. 4-5, where a detailed view of the meshes near of the bow of the floating body are shown on the right panels). In the mesh shown in Fig. 4, the wet surface of the Wigley hull and the free surface have been refined in order to capture accurately the Kelvin wake pattern. This mesh contains 2.8 millions tetrahedra. In the mesh shown in Fig. 5, the wet surface of the floating body and the downstream hull edge are only refined. In that case, the mesh only has 4.2×10^5 tetrahedra approximately. To illustrate the robust numerical behaviour of the proposed method with respect to the mesh, the coarser mesh has been used to analyse the free surface elevation close to the Wigley hull (see Sect. 7.4 for more details).

7.2 PML absorption profile

The definition of the absorption profile in the PML, $\sigma_r : [R, R_\infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$, involves the prescription of an increasing non-negative function. In this work, a high-order polynomial approximation of the following singular absorption profile was used:

$$\sigma_r(r) = \frac{\sigma_0}{R_\infty - r} - \frac{\sigma_0}{R_\infty - R},$$

where σ_0 is a given positive parameter. In this manner, the pointwise values of the singular PML absorption profile and its polynomial approximation are identical at the quadrature nodes used in the finite element discretization, and at the same time, the PML coefficients involved in the weak formulation are well defined on the entire discrete computational domain.

In order to select an optimal value for σ_0 in the PML absorption profile, a reference solution was computed in a very large domain, which is truncated with homogeneous boundary conditions. For this purpose, a computational fluid domain with an

Figure 4: Computational mesh with a refinement on the free surface and on the wet surface, where the fluid and PML subdomains are highlighted in green and yellow respectively (left). A closer detail of the mesh refinement on the bow of the Wigley hull (right).

Figure 5: Computational mesh with a refinement on the wet surface, where the fluid and PML subdomains are highlighted in green and yellow respectively (left). A closer detail of the mesh refinement on the bow of the Wigley hull (right).

exterior radius of 40 m has been chosen to compute the reference solution. Then, a quantitative comparison is made to evaluate the relation between the reference result (computed in the large domain without PML), ϕ_{ref} , and the solution ϕ of the problem (19) (computed in a smaller domain truncated with a PML layer). More precisely, the L^2 -relative difference between both potentials is computed on the free surface by means of

$$\frac{\|\phi_{ref} - \phi\|_2}{\|\phi_{ref}\|_2} = \frac{(\int_{\partial\mathcal{A}f} |\phi_{ref} - \phi|^2 dA_x)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{(\int_{\partial\mathcal{A}f} |\phi_{ref}|^2 dA_x)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad (29)$$

in six different numerical simulations with Froude numbers $Fr = 0.25, 0.267, 0.289, 0.316, 0.354, 0.408$. After a swept in σ_0 from 10^{-3} to 60, the value $\sigma_0 = 0.05$ was chosen since it minimizes the arithmetic mean of the L^2 -relative differences computed from the six numerical approximations (see Fig. 6).

Additionally, Fig. 7 shows a qualitative comparison between the reference potential and the potential obtained with the PML ($\sigma_0 = 0.05$) in the smallest computational domain, for the case of $Fr = 0.25$ (notice that only a portion of the largest domain used for computing the reference solution is depicted).

Figure 6: Mean relative difference computed from six different numerical simulations plotted with respect to σ_0 (Right: range $\sigma_0 \in [0, 0.2]$; left: range $\sigma_0 \in [0, 60]$).

7.3 Numerical comparison with experimental data and full Navier-Stokes approximations

In this section, the proposed model, the classical linear potential model, and the full Navier-Stokes with two species are compared with the available experimental data at $Fr = 0.267$. More precisely, the classical linear potential model has been already described in Remark 5.1 and a turbulence $k-\omega$ model coupled with the full Navier-Stokes equations (see [Wil06]) was solved in a computational domain with two species: air over the water to model the free surface boundary. Both fluids have been considered as incompressible. Regarding the used computational domains, the classical linear model and the proposed one have been discretized using the same mesh. Analogous upwinding and PML techniques have been used in both cases. In the case of the Navier-Stokes model, a prism was chosen and no PML layers are involved in its simulation. Analogous to the linear potential models, the symmetry with respect to the longitudinal plane of the Wigley hull has been used to restrict the computational domain to one half. In order to recover the interface between the two fluid phases, a refinement was imposed on the plane $z = 0$ and, thus, its discretization involves a mesh with 33 millions of tetrahedra approximately. The full two-phases Navier-Stokes model has been solved numerically using Ansys Fluent. A set of control points located on the wake support has been used to define the convergence stop criterion. Once constant values are reached at those points, the Navier-Stokes approximation is assumed steady-state and the iterative process is stopped. The maximum number of iterations has been fixed to 10000.

Fig. 8 shows the numerical approximation of the non-dimensional free surface elevation as a function of the non-dimensional position along the Wigley hull waterline, x/L_w , for the three models as well as the experimental results with $Fr = 0.267$. For the linear models, the finest mesh (shown in Fig. 4) has been used and the numerical free surface elevation was computed by

$$\eta_a = -\frac{1}{g} \text{grad}_a \phi_a \cdot \mathbf{v}^{ap}, \quad (30)$$

and it is suggested in [GMHF15]. In all cases, for a direct comparison with the available experimental data, [KMI⁺83], the non-dimensional quantity $\tilde{\eta} = 2g\eta_a/|\mathbf{v}^{ap}|$ has been plotted.

In order to compare the flow downstream, Fig. 9 shows the three components of the velocity computed using these three different models. The full two-phases Navier-Stokes model and the proposed model show a similar pattern, except for the region of the wake which is aligned with the edge on the stern. However, the full two-phases Navier-Stokes model seems to damp the wake oscillations more than the proposed model as it can be observed in Fig. 8. Regarding the classical linear model, the wake angle (angle given between the main Wigley axis and the line where the maxima/minima of the wake pattern are located) and the amplitude of the velocity potential is smaller than in the other two models.

Figure 7: Left: potential field, ϕ_a , for the experiment of the Wigley hull free to sink and trim with $Fr = 0.25$ obtained using the present model with PML. Right: a zoom of the reference potential field without PML in a big domain with 40 meters radius.

Figure 8: Non-dimensional free surface elevation for the Kelvin wake generated by the Wigley hull with $Fr = 0.267$ (experimental results from [KMI⁺83] depicted in orange dots, classical linear model in the red dashed line, Navier-Stokes results in the green dotted line, and results from the present model in the continuous blue line).

7.4 Numerical comparison with respect to the classical model

In Figs. 10-11, the free surface elevations (computed as it is described in Sect. 7.3) for the six experiments reported in [KMI⁺83] are compared with respect to the numerical results of the proposed model and the classical linear model for two different meshes. On the one hand, Fig. 10 contains the results for the mesh with a refinement on the free surface and the wet surface of the hull. On the other hand, Fig. 11 shows the results for the mesh with a refinement only on the wet surface. In view of both figures, the proposed model exhibits a robust behaviour to compute accurately the free surface elevation along the waterline for the six experiments (independently of the refinement type used in the mesh), while the classical linear model presents instabilities on the stern for some experiments.

Figure 9: Numerical approximation of the velocity field for the Kelvin wake generated by the Wigley hull with $Fr = 0.267$ using the full Navier-Stokes model, the present model and the classical linear model (each row uses the same color scale).

Figure 10: Non dimensional free surface elevation results at different Froude numbers (Fr) using the mesh shown in Fig. 4 and compared with respect to experimental data (experimental results from [KMI⁺83] depicted in orange dots, classical linear model in red dashed lines and results from the present model in continuous blue lines).

Figure 11: Non dimensional free surface elevation results at different Froude numbers (Fr) using the mesh shown in Fig. 5 and compared with respect to experimental data (experimental results from [KMI⁺83] depicted in orange dots, classical linear model in red dashed lines and results from the present model in continuous blue lines).

8 Conclusions

A novel linear potential model for the free surface flow produced by the presence of a floating rigid body in motion have been derived by using an ALE formulation and a subsequent linearisation. The difficulties associated with its numerical resolution have been pointed out and discussed in detail: the convective term stated on the free surface boundary and the truncation of the unbounded physical domain where an outgoing radiation condition is imposed.

In order to overcome these difficulties, a new approach to upwind the convective term have been developed, which avoids a spurious numerical behaviour when it is combined with a PML technique. The use of a PML layer with a singular absorbing profile guarantee an accurate damping of the solution in the radial direction even when the computational domain is truncated near the floating body. The proposed methodology has been validated by comparing their numerical results with respect to the available experimental data from the Wigley hull benchmark.

Regarding the current and future work, the numerical methodology developed in the present paper is being extended to solve the unsteady problem not only to simulate the Kelvin wake pattern but also to include incoming sea surface waves.

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A Proof of Theorem 3.1

Before being in a position to show Theorem 3.1, the material description of a spatial field must be defined explicitly and it is necessary to introduce two auxiliary lemmas about the relation of the gradients of motions Y_f and Z_f .

Definition A.1. Let $f : \mathcal{T} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a spatial field and $g : \mathcal{A} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a field defined in the AL configuration. Their respective material descriptions are defined by

$$f_m(p, t) := f(X_f(p, t), t) \quad \text{and} \quad g_m(p, t) := g(Z_f(p, t), t),$$

where X_f denotes the total motion of the fluid and Z_f the underlying motion used in the AL description.

Besides, recall that subscript a denotes the AL description (see Sect. 3).

Lemma A.1. Let X_f be a motion, Y_f and Z_f be the decomposition described in Sect. 3, and let \mathbf{F}_{X_f} , \mathbf{F}_{Y_f} and \mathbf{F}_{Z_f} denote their respective gradients. Then, it holds

$$\left(\mathbf{F}_{Z_f}^{-t}\right)_a \left(- \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_{X_f}^t}{\partial t} \right)_a \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t} + \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_{Z_f}^t}{\partial t} \right)_a \right) = - \left(\frac{\partial \left(\mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^t \right)_m}{\partial t} \right) \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t}.$$

Proof. Firstly, since $X(p, t) = Y(Z(p, t), t)$, a straightforward use of the chain rule leads to

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_{X_f}^t}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\mathbf{F}_{Z_f}^t \left(\mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^t \right)_m \right) = \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_{Z_f}^t}{\partial t} \left(\mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^t \right)_m + \mathbf{F}_{Z_f}^t \frac{\partial \left(\mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^t \right)_m}{\partial t}, \quad (31)$$

and then, replacing the time derivative of $\mathbf{F}_{X_f}^t$ by the expression written above in the left-hand side of (31), it holds

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\mathbf{F}_{Z_f}^{-t}\right)_a \left(- \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_{X_f}^t}{\partial t} \right)_a \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t} + \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_{Z_f}^t}{\partial t} \right)_a \right) \\ &= \left(\mathbf{F}_{Z_f}^{-t}\right)_a \left[- \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_{Z_f}^t}{\partial t} \right)_a - \left(\mathbf{F}_{Z_f}^t \right)_a \left(\frac{\partial \left(\mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^t \right)_m}{\partial t} \right) \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t} + \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_{Z_f}^t}{\partial t} \right)_a \right] = - \left(\frac{\partial \left(\mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^t \right)_m}{\partial t} \right) \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t}. \end{aligned}$$

□

Lemma A.2. Let φ be a potential field associated with the irrotational motion X_f of an incompressible and inviscid fluid such that $\text{grad } \varphi(x, t) = \mathbf{v}(x, t) := \dot{X}_f(P_{X_f}(x, t), t)$, where P_{X_f} denotes the reference mapping of X_f . Let Y_f and Z_f be the decomposition of motion X_f described in Sect. 3, and \mathbf{F}_{Y_f} , \mathbf{F}_{Z_f} and \mathbf{F}_{X_f} denote their respective gradients. Then, it holds

$$\left((\text{grad } \varphi)' \right)_a = \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t} \left[- \left(\frac{\partial \left(\mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^t \right)_m}{\partial t} \right) \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t} \text{grad}_a \varphi_a + \text{grad}_a \frac{\partial \varphi_a}{\partial t} + \mathbf{grad}_a \text{grad}_a \varphi_a \mathbf{d}_a \right].$$

Proof. Firstly, it is straightforward to check that

$$((\text{grad } \varphi)')_a = (((\text{grad } \varphi)_m)')_a, \quad \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_{X_f}^{-t}}{\partial t} = -\mathbf{F}_{X_f}^{-t} \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_{X_f}^t}{\partial t} \mathbf{F}_{X_f}^{-t}.$$

Additionally, using the chain of rule it holds $(\text{grad } \varphi)_m = \mathbf{F}_{X_f}^{-t} \text{grad}_m \varphi_m$ and $\text{grad}_m \varphi_m = \mathbf{F}_{Z_f}^t (\text{grad}_a \varphi_a)_m$. Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} ((\text{grad } \varphi)_m)' &= \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\text{grad } \varphi)_m = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\mathbf{F}_{X_f}^{-t} \text{grad}_m \varphi_m) = \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_{X_f}^{-t}}{\partial t} \text{grad}_m \varphi_m + \mathbf{F}_{X_f}^{-t} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\text{grad}_m \varphi_m) \\ &= \mathbf{F}_{X_f}^{-t} \left[-\frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_{X_f}^t}{\partial t} \mathbf{F}_{X_f}^{-t} \mathbf{F}_{Z_f}^t (\text{grad}_a \varphi_a)_m + \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\mathbf{F}_{Z_f}^t (\text{grad}_a \varphi_a)_m) \right] \\ &= \mathbf{F}_{X_f}^{-t} \left[-\frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_{X_f}^t}{\partial t} (\mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t})_m (\text{grad}_a \varphi_a)_m + \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_{Z_f}^t}{\partial t} (\text{grad}_a \varphi_a)_m + \mathbf{F}_{Z_f}^t \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\text{grad}_a \varphi_a)_m \right] \\ &= (\mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t})_m \left[\mathbf{F}_{Z_f}^{-t} \left(-\frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_{X_f}^t}{\partial t} (\mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t})_m + \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_{Z_f}^t}{\partial t} \right) (\text{grad}_a \varphi_a)_m + \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\text{grad}_a \varphi_a)_m \right], \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

because $\mathbf{F}_{X_f}^{-t} \mathbf{F}_{Z_f}^t = (\mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t})_m$ from $\mathbf{F}_{X_f}(p, t) = \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}(Z_f(p, t), t) \mathbf{F}_{Z_f}(p, t)$ which, in turn, is direct from (6). Moreover, working with the last term of the expression above,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\text{grad}_a \varphi_a)_m = \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\text{grad}_a \varphi_a) \right)_m + (\mathbf{grad}_a \text{grad}_a \varphi_a)_m \frac{\partial Z_f}{\partial t} = \left(\text{grad}_a \frac{\partial \varphi_a}{\partial t} \right)_m + (\mathbf{grad}_a \text{grad}_a \varphi_a)_m \mathbf{d}.$$

Then, replacing the expression above in the last term of (32), it holds

$$((\text{grad } \varphi)_m)' = (\mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t})_m \left[\mathbf{F}_{Z_f}^{-t} \left(-\frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_{X_f}^t}{\partial t} (\mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t})_m + \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_{Z_f}^t}{\partial t} \right) (\text{grad}_a \varphi_a)_m + \left(\text{grad}_a \frac{\partial \varphi_a}{\partial t} \right)_m + (\mathbf{grad}_a \text{grad}_a \varphi_a)_m \mathbf{d} \right]$$

and hence, its AL description is given by

$$((\text{grad } \varphi)')_a = \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t} \left[(\mathbf{F}_{Z_f}^{-t})_a \left(-\left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_{X_f}^t}{\partial t} \right)_a \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t} + \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_{Z_f}^t}{\partial t} \right)_a \right) \text{grad}_a \varphi_a + \text{grad}_a \frac{\partial \varphi_a}{\partial t} + \mathbf{grad}_a \text{grad}_a \varphi_a \mathbf{d}_a \right].$$

The result follows by using Lemma A.1. □

Now the proof of Theorem 3.1 can be derived straightforwardly as follows.

Proof. Firstly, the motion equation (1) in AL variables becomes

$$\rho_f ((\text{grad } \varphi)')_a + (\text{grad } \pi)_a = -(\text{grad } (\rho_f g x_3))_a$$

and, equivalently,

$$\rho_f ((\text{grad } \varphi)')_a + \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t} \text{grad}_a \pi_a = -\mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t} \text{grad}_a (\rho_f g Y_{f3}).$$

Then, using Lemma A.2,

$$\rho_f \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t} \left[-\left(\frac{\partial (\mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^t)_m}{\partial t} \right)_a \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t} \text{grad}_a \varphi_a + \text{grad}_a \frac{\partial \varphi_a}{\partial t} + \mathbf{grad}_a \text{grad}_a \varphi_a \mathbf{d}_a \right] + \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t} \text{grad}_a \pi_a = -\mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t} \text{grad}_a (\rho_f g Y_{f3}),$$

and multiplying by $\mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^t$ both sides of the equation above, it holds

$$-\rho_f \left(\frac{\partial (\mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^t)_m}{\partial t} \right)_a \mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^{-t} \text{grad}_a \varphi_a + \rho_f \mathbf{grad}_a \text{grad}_a \varphi_a \mathbf{d}_a + \rho_f \text{grad}_a \frac{\partial \varphi_a}{\partial t} + \text{grad}_a \pi_a + \text{grad}_a (\rho_f g Y_{f3}) = \mathbf{0}.$$

Finally, the result is obtained from the equation above combined with

$$\left(\frac{\partial (\mathbf{F}_{Y_f}^t)_m}{\partial t} \right)_a = \left(\mathbf{grad}_a \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_{Y_f}}{\partial t} \right)^t + \mathbf{grad}_a (\mathbf{grad}_a \mathbf{u}_{Y_f})^t \mathbf{d}_a,$$

where $\mathbf{u}_{Y_f}(z, t) := Y(z, t) - z$. □

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